

Eligibility criteria: The nexus of health and labour exploitation among migrant populations in the Eastern Mediterranean region and Türkiye: a scoping review

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	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Population	Migrants irrespective of their age, nationality, gender, ethnicity, and migration status.	Other population groups
Concept	Studies that include cases of labour exploitation in migrant populations, reports on labour exploitation-associated health outcomes, and related aspects of healthcare access will be included.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Studies focusing only on sex trafficking will be excluded. - Studies focusing on labour exploitation in populations other than migrants. - Studies focusing on labour exploitation in migrant populations without addressing associated health issues. - Studies focusing on migrants' health without addressing relevant labour exploitation aspects. - Studies focusing on populations outside of the geographic scope.
Context	The WHO-designated Eastern Mediterranean region countries and Türkiye that host migrants. The list includes Afghanistan, Bahrain, Djibouti, Egypt, Iran, Iraq, Jordan, Kuwait, Lebanon, Libya, Morocco, Oman, Pakistan, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Somalia, Sudan, Syria, Tunisia, United Arab Emirates, Yemen, and Türkiye.	Countries or regions not included in this list.
Types of outcomes	The outcomes have to specifically consider changes to migrants' health and well-being or access to healthcare in relation to experiences of labour exploitation	
Type of evidence	This scoping review will consider both experimental and quasi-experimental research designs, including randomised controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials, before and after studies and interrupted time-series studies. Analytical observational studies, including prospective and retrospective cohort studies, case-control studies and analytical cross-sectional studies, will be considered for inclusion. This review will also consider descriptive observational study designs such as case series, individual case	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Newsletters, media articles and blogs. - Articles not available.

	reports and descriptive cross-sectional studies. This scoping review will also consider systematic reviews that meet eligibility criteria. Qualitative data such as ethnographic, narrative, phenomenology, grounded theory, case study or action research studies will also be considered. The review will also consider grey literature, including technical reports, government documents, thesis or dissertations and research reports. Reports published on websites of international organisations such as the International Labor Organization, UNICEF, World Bank, UN Women, and Save the Children.	
Publication year	Any study published from March 2011 to the present	Any study published before March 2011
Language	English	Other languages with no translation available